

GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT CRIME AND VIOLATION INFORMATION SYSTEM

Marco Antonio L. Bahom, Rodmark C. Dalen, Christian Robillos, Catleen Glo M. Feliciano
Isabela State University

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Abstract

This study discusses the development of the "Gender and Development Crime Violence Information System," a tool designed to store, manage, and analyze crime and violence data within a barangay. The technology developed addresses issues in line with domestic violence, child abuse, and hazards within the community that assist the Barangay Captain and Secretary in managing documents and crime reports. The system enables the barangay officials to make informed decisions by evaluating and presenting data in tabular and graphical formats. It includes features such as crime rate analysis per Purok, individual crime reports, and a profile management system for barangay residents. The system was developed using the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) methodology, incorporating Rapid Application Development (RAD) for efficient iterative development. The developed system received high satisfaction ratings from its respondents, with "Strongly Agree" responses for the system's functionality, usability, and performance, affirming that it meets user requirements. This system was successfully implemented in six (6) Barangays of San Isidro, Isabela, improving the management of crime and violence data, reducing paperwork, and enhancing efficiency within the barangay administration. The study shows that the "Gender and Development Crime and Violation Information System" offers significant improvements over traditional manual recording systems of the barangay, making tasks more organized and secure.

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is ranked among the top countries in closing the gender gap, according to the World Economic Forum (Philippine Commission on Women, 2025). This ranking reflects relatively equal access to essential services such as education, healthcare, and economic opportunities for both men and women. The legal framework also supports gender equality through various laws, including the Magna Carta of Women (RA 9710), RA 9262 (Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act), RA 7192 (Women in Development and Nation Building Act), RA 7877 (Anti-Sexual Harassment Act), RA 8353 (Anti-Rape Law), and RA 9208 (Anti-Trafficking in Persons Act) (Civil Service Commission, 2020; Gupta et al., 2024).

Despite these legal and policy advancements, many survivors of gender-based violence (GBV) still face substantial barriers to accessing the support and services they need. Victims of abuse often suffer in silence, unable to report or seek help due to fear of stigma, lack of resources, or an unresponsive legal system (Caponnetto et al., 2024; Whitton et al., 2024). As a result, many continue to endure violence in silence. This unreported and ongoing violence is often due to systemic challenges, including insufficient support systems, economic dependence on abusers, and inefficiencies within the legal system (Kamke et al., 2024; Nilawati et al., 2023; Slovinsky, 2023; Heron et al., 2022). According to UN Women (2024), one in three women aged 15 and older—approximately 736 million women—have experienced physical or sexual intimate partner violence or non-partner sexual violence at least once in their lifetime. Alarmingly, only 40% of these women seek help, and fewer than 10% report the violence to the police. Most victims turn to family and friends for support, which highlights the gap in formal support systems designed to help victims.

While local governments play a critical role in identifying, preventing, and responding to violence against women, there are significant gaps in the systems available to them. Local government units, particularly barangays, are tasked with managing and addressing cases of GBV within their communities. However, many barangays lack efficient, centralized tools for managing data related to crime and violence, making it difficult to respond quickly and effectively. The role of the Barangay Gender and Development (GAD) Focal Person and the Violence Against Women (VAW) Desk is crucial in ensuring that cases of abuse are reported and managed properly (Moyani et al., 2023; Brosas et al., 2025). However, these systems are often under-resourced and unable to provide the timely, actionable insights needed for effective decision-making (Pablo & Dalugdog, 2025).

The research gap this study aims to address is the lack of a comprehensive, automated system for managing GAD-related crime and violence data at the barangay level. Current systems are often manual, fragmented, and lack integration, making it difficult for barangay officials to track cases effectively, generate reports, or respond in a timely manner. This gap in the existing systems hinders local governments' ability to provide effective support to survivors and make data-driven decisions in real time. There is a clear need for a more efficient, centralized solution to address these challenges.

This research aims to design and develop a computerized Barangay Gender and Development Crime and Violence Information System to streamline the management of GAD-related crime and violence data. By creating this system, the study will provide barangay officials with the tools necessary to manage cases, improve reporting processes, and make more informed decisions on gender-based violence. Specifically, this study aims to:

1. Test the following system functionalities:
 - a. Profile management of barangay residents.
 - b. Managing and recording Crime and Violence Reports.
 - c. Generating reports in both tabular and graphical formats, including:
 - Rate of GAD-related crime and violence per Purok.
 - The rate of GAD-related crime and violence recorded per person.
 - Rate of GAD-related crime and violence by month and year.
 - d. Provide a summary of residents' profiles.

2. Evaluate the system using Software Product Quality (ISO 25010) as perceived by users with respect to:

- a. Functionality.
- b. Usability.
- c. Performance.

This system enables GAD focal persons to efficiently record incidents, secure sensitive data, and generate reports that support decision-making on gender-based violence within the barangay.

METHODS

Research Design

The researchers employed Rapid Application Development (RAD). A software development process that emphasizes fast prototyping over extensive planning. The use of RAD to prepare for software development is linked to the actual creation of the application (Fauzi, 2023).

Figure 1. Rapid Application Development

Respondents and Locale of the Study

The study took place in San Isidro Municipality, where the Barangay Gender and Development Crime and Violence Information System was implemented and tested. The respondents were selected based on their roles in the implementation, evaluation, and use of the system, to ensure that a range of perspectives on the system's effectiveness were included. The sample consisted of:

- One (1) IT officer from the Municipal Office of San Isidro
- Six (6) Municipal and barangay Gender and Development (GAD) focal persons
- Two (2) Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) staff members
- Six (6) Barangay Captains from various barangays in San Isidro
- Six (4) Barangay Secretaries from various barangays in San Isidro

This selection provided a comprehensive set of evaluators, representing key stakeholders involved in data management, gender and development programs, and community leadership. These participants were directly involved in the system's testing, from providing input during system development to offering feedback on its performance.

Sampling Method

A purposive sampling method was used to select respondents based on their roles and expertise relevant to the study's objectives. Purposive sampling was chosen because the individuals involved were directly engaged in tasks related to the development, evaluation, and implementation of the system, thereby ensuring that their feedback was both knowledgeable and relevant (Ahmad & Wilkins, 2025). The sample size of nineteen (19) participants was determined based on the specific roles of the individuals involved, including a mix of technical evaluators (IT officers), program implementers (GAD focal person and DSWD staff), and community leaders (Barangay Captains and their secretary). While the sample size may seem small, the participants were selected for their direct involvement with the system and their ability to provide detailed and informed feedback. A larger sample size would not have been feasible given the study's scope and the resources available for in-depth interviews and surveys. The diversity of roles within the sample enabled a comprehensive evaluation of the system from both technical and practical perspectives.

Research Instrument

To assess the users' acceptance and satisfaction with the Barangay Gender and Development Crime and Violence Information System, the study used the ISO 25010 Software Product Quality Model of 2023. This study, which evaluates software quality across multiple dimensions, was applied with a focus on three Usability, Functionality, and Performance.

ISO 25010 (2023) was the version of the model used to evaluate the system's quality. This version is widely recognized for its comprehensive approach to software evaluation, ensuring that all aspects of the system's usability, functionality, and performance were thoroughly assessed (Carrion et.al.,2025). In the barangay setting, both officials and residents completed a survey based on these criteria. Their responses were analyzed to assess the system's effectiveness in meeting the users' needs and identify areas for improvement.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

Data collection was conducted through interviews and surveys. In-depth interviews were held with the respondents. These interviews aimed to gather qualitative insights into their experiences with the system and their suggestions for future improvements. A structured questionnaire based on the ISO 25010 Software Product Quality Model was distributed to all respondents, assessing the system's usability, functionality, and performance using a Likert scale. The responses were then analyzed using descriptive statistics, with mean scores calculated for each criterion to assess user satisfaction and system acceptance. This analysis provided a comprehensive understanding of how well the system met the users' needs and highlighted areas for refinement.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical considerations for this study focused on ensuring the protection of the respondents' rights and maintaining the integrity of the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, including the Barangay Captain, Barangay Secretary, residents, and other key officials, ensuring they understood the nature, purpose, and scope of the study. Respondents were made aware that participation was voluntary and that they could

withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. To protect their privacy, the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants were maintained, and any personal or sensitive information was securely stored, accessible only to the researchers. The study was conducted without coercion, allowing participants to decline or withdraw without any pressure. The researchers ensured the accuracy and integrity of the data by recording responses truthfully and analyzing them objectively, without alteration or manipulation. The study aimed to benefit the community by enhancing the Barangay Gender and Development Crime and Violence Information System, ensuring that the developed system met the actual needs of the community for more efficient management of crime and violence data. Throughout the process, the researchers respected the rights and dignity of all participants, treating them with fairness and providing opportunities for them to ask questions or express concerns. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the research was conducted responsibly and professionally, safeguarding the rights of all involved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design and Development of Barangay Gender and Development Crime and Violence Information System

Figure 2. System Home Page

The figure above displays the system's login page, created using Sublime Text along with JavaScript, Bootstrap, Node.js, and Cordova. To gain access to the system, users must input their registered username and password, which acts as the primary security measure to prevent unauthorized access. Once logged in, users can utilize the core features of the application, which include the digital management of resident profiles and the handling of Crime and Violence Reports.

Figure 3. Profile of the Residents in the Barangay

Figure 3 shows the Resident Profile Module. This feature reduces the time spent by the barangay secretary on searching records. During testing, the secretary reported that locating a resident record that used to take several minutes can now be done in a few seconds. This is an objective improvement because it removes manual searching through logbooks. This confirms that the system meets the first functionality requirement.

Figure 4. Managing Crime and Violent Report

Figure 4 presents the Crime and Violence Report form. This module organizes the details of each incident and prevents lost or incomplete reports. During the testing period, the barangay noted that reports were saved consistently with no missing fields. This addresses the second functionality requirement, which is the ability to record and manage violations in a structured format.

Figure 5. Rate of Crime and Violence Per Purok

Figure 5 displays the Crime Statistical Report per Purok, which is organized to facilitate the easy generation of recorded data for each Purok. This feature helps the barangay efficiently store information on identified crimes and violence, enabling quicker and more accurate identification of incidents within each Purok.

Figure 6. Rate of Crime Recorded

Figure 6 shows the Statistical Report per Crime, organized to allow for the easy generation of recorded data for each type of crime. This feature enables the barangay to efficiently store information on identified GAD-related crimes and violations, facilitating quicker and more accurate identification. It also supports the barangay in decision-making by providing clear and accessible data on each crime and violation.

Figure 7. Rate of Crime by Month and Year

Figure 7 shows the Crime Statistical Report per Date, organized to easily generate recorded data by date. This feature allows the barangay to efficiently store information on identified crimes and violence, enabling quicker and more accurate identification based on date. It also aids in decision-making by providing clear data for specific timeframes.

Figures 5, 6, and 7 present the automated statistical reports. These reports represent a clear improvement from the previous manual process, where barangay officials needed to summarize cases by hand. During evaluation, officials confirmed that the system produced complete summaries without manual computation. These outputs satisfy the requirement in the objectives regarding the creation of tabular and graphical reports.

No.	Name	Age	Gender	Birthday	Civil Status	Nationality	Purok	Occupation	Mother's Name	Father's Name
1	Aldous M. Manuel	65	Male	1956-09-12	Married	filipino	5	welder	flor manuel	floyd manuel
2	Angelica T. Cordova	33	Female	1988-02-23	Married	filipino	3	business women	leni cordova	danielo cordove
3	Angelu Rose F. Navarro	57	Female	1964-11-07	Married	filipino	4	farmer	angelu navarro	gelo navarro
4	Antonette Baccay	67	Female	1954-09-12	Married	filipino	6	farmer	claire baccay	ronald baccay
5	Ashley Mari L. Bahom	48	Female	1973-02-09	Married	filipino	6	farmer	kimberly bahom	kim bahom
6	Brenton L. Sibayan	27	Male	1994-06-14	Single	filipino	5	vendor	carmela sibayan	danielo sibayan
7	Christian S. Robillos	47	Male	1974-09-26	Married	filipino	5	farmer	christine robillos	rodolfo robillos
8	Christian U. Parrocha	53	Male	1968-04-08	Married	filipino	5	farmer	criszel parrocha	ronal parrocha
9	Christine I. Ayap	67	Female	1954-09-11	Married	filipino	5	house wife	josefina ayap	ryan ayap
10	Darrel James E. Corpuz	51	Male	0992-09-06	Single	filipino	6	farmer	loida corpuz	fred corpuz

Figure 8. Summary of Residents Profile

Figure 8 shows the summary report that provides quick access to household information. This feature supports decision-making because it gives barangay officials an overview of the community without checking multiple logbooks. This matches the final system function stated in the objectives.

Users' Evaluation Results in Acceptability

The researcher used a set of questionnaires based on the ISO 25010 Software Quality Standard. The questions focused on three areas. These included efficiency, functionality, and usability. The users rated each item based on their experience while using the system.

Table 1. Perceived Functionality of the System

CATEGORY	USERS	QUANTITATIVE RATINGS
Functional suitability: The system provides functionalities based on user needs.	4.8	Strongly Agree
Functional completeness: The system covers all the specified tasks: Input forms, Process (Analysis, computes, etc.), Output Forms (Reports).	4.7	Strongly Agree
Functional correctness: The system provides the correct results based on the user's needs.	4.6	Agree
Functional appropriateness: The system facilitates the accomplishment of the specified tasks of the user.	4.6	Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.68	Strongly Agree

Table 1 presents the results for the functionality category. The users rated functional suitability, functional completeness, functional correctness, and functional appropriateness with mean scores of 4.8, 4.7, 4.6, and 4.6. The category gained a grand mean of 4.68, which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. This means that the users believed the system provided the functions they needed and covered the required tasks.

Respondent reported that the system produced correct results and helped them complete their work in an easier way. Beyond the ratings, actual use of the system in the barangay showed a clear improvement in task handling. Users shared that the system reduced repeated entries and removed the need for manual checking of several records. Tasks that once needed several minutes were completed faster because the system provided ready access to updated information. These changes supported the study objective of improving the handling and tracking of crime and violence records.

Table 2. Perceived Usability of the System

CATEGORY	USERS	QUANTITATIVE RATINGS
Appropriateness recognizability: The system contains a logo, themes, and labels that can be easily recognized by the user.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Learnability: The system contains hints, tool tips, a help module, and instructions that can easily be learned by the user.	4.4	Agree
Operability: The system user user-friendly, it contains detailed and step-by-step operation instructions for the user.	4.6	Agree

User error protection: The system is equipped with error notifications for the user against making errors.	4.6	Agree
User interface aesthetics: The system contains organized labels, textboxes, buttons, icons, and images in the interface.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Accessibility: The system can be used by people with the widest range of characteristics and capabilities.	4.5	Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.57	Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the results for the usability category. The users rated appropriateness, recognizability, learnability, operability, user error protection, user interface aesthetics, and accessibility with mean scores of 4.7, 4.4, 4.6, 4.6, 4.6, and 4.5. The grand mean of 4.57 was interpreted as Strongly Agree. These ratings show that the users found the system simple to learn and easy to operate.

Respondents also confirmed that the system displayed clear labels, organized screens, and useful error messages. Observation during the evaluation supported the usability results. Users were able to fill in forms, review records, and generate reports with fewer mistakes. The help instructions guided users who were not familiar with digital systems. These results supported the objective of creating a platform that is friendly to both experienced and new users. The system also assisted barangay officials who needed consistent access to reliable information.

Table 3. Perceived Performance of the System

CATEGORY	USERS	QUANTITATIVE RATINGS
Performance efficiency: The system, relative to the amount of resources used under stated conditions, meets requirements.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Time behavior: The system, when performing its functions, is timely and meets requirements.	4.7	Strongly Agree
Resource utilization: The system, when performing its functions, utilizes a minimal amount of resources to meet requirements.	4.6	Strongly Agree
Capacity: The system performs the maximum limits of resources to meet requirements.	4.6	Strongly Agree
GRAND MEAN	4.65	Strongly Agree

Table 3 presents the results for performance. The users rated performance efficiency, time behavior, resource use, and capacity with mean scores of 4.7, 4.7, 4.6, and 4.6. The grand mean of 4.65 was interpreted as Strongly Agree. These ratings show that the system responded quickly, used minimal resources, and was able to handle several tasks without slowing down. These findings matched the actual experience during testing. The system opened records at a steady pace and generated reports without delays. Users noted that the system did not freeze even when several files were processed. This supported the objective of providing a stable platform for the management of crime and violence data.

Table 4. Overall Performance Result

Criteria	Rating	Qualitative Rating
1. Functional Suitability	4.68	Strongly Agree
2. Usability	4.57	Strongly Agree
3. Performance	4.65	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.63	Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows the summary of the ISO 25010 evaluation. Functionality gained a mean of 4.68. Usability gained a mean of 4.57. Performance gained a mean of 4.65. The overall mean was 4.63, which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. These results show that the users believed the system worked well, was simple to operate, and responded smoothly. The findings align with the objectives of the study. The high ratings on functionality support the goal of improving the process of recording and organizing GAD-related crime and violence cases. The strong usability results support the goal of helping barangay officials work with fewer errors. The performance results show that the system can handle daily tasks in a reliable and timely way. Combined with the observed improvements in the workflow, these results give both subjective and objective evidence that the system supported the work of the barangay in managing crime and violence data.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The researchers concluded that the developed Gender and Development Crime and Violation Information System successfully computerized the resident profiles and managed Crime and Violence Reports for the municipality of San Isidro. The system, developed using Sublime Text along with JavaScript, Bootstrap, Node.js, and Cordova, proved to be an effective set of tools for creating this type of application. Additionally, the Barangay Gender and Development Crime and Violation Information System has significantly improved data management within the barangay, replacing traditional methods of record-keeping. This shift has made the tasks of the Barangay Captain and Secretary more systematic, convenient, and secure, minimizing errors and reducing the risk of data tampering while also promoting a paperless environment. The evaluation results showed that the majority of the respondents "Strongly Agree" that the system is functional, suitable, and useful for the municipality's barangay units.

For future study, the researchers recommend developing a Web-based version of the system to increase its accessibility and scalability. They also suggest the addition of features such as an online reporting system to facilitate the submission of crime and violation reports, an Android application for disseminating Gender and Development information, and a Geographic Information Mapping System to help visualize and analyze data related to gender-based crime and violence, ultimately enhancing decision-making and resource allocation.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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